

SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC ESTIMATION OF AZELNIDIPINE AND TELMISARTAN IN PHARMACEUTICAL DOSAGE FORM BY FIRST-ORDER DERIVATIVE METHOD

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ABSTRACT:

The estimation of Azelnidipine and Telmisartan in its tablet formulation has been devised and validated using simple and accurate UV- spectrophotometric methods, for Methanol was used to prepare the azelnidipine and telmisartan standard and sample solutions. For the first order derivative UV-spectrophotometric technique, azelnidipine was estimated at a wavelength of 271 nm and telmisartan a wavelength of 234 nm. Beer's law was obeyed in the concentration ranges of the drugs azelnidipine and telmisartan ranged 1 to 6 g/ml and 5 to 30 g/ml, respectively, with coefficients of correlation of 0.9977 and 0.998. According to ICH criteria, the method was tested and validated for a number of factors. For the above-mentioned method, the precision expressed as the relative standard deviation was 1.780% and 1.467, respectively. Azelnidipine and Telmisartan concentrations in pharmaceutical formulations were effectively determined using the proposed methods. The analysis's results were statistically validated and were found to be satisfactory. The proposed methods are simple, easy to use, economical, and require relatively inexpensive tools.

Keywords: Azelnidipine, Telmisartan, first-order derivative spectroscopy, methanol.

INTRODUCTION

Azelnidipine is a lipophilic calcium channel antagonist. The compound is known by the chemical name O-3-[1-[di (phenyl) methyl] azetidino-3-yl] O-5-propane-2-yl 2-amino-6-methyl-4-(3-nitrophenyl)-1,4-dihydropyridine-3,5-dicarboxylate. Ca⁺ ions that are outside the cardiac muscle and vascular smooth muscle can be restrained by azelnidipine. Through the cell membrane, they penetrate the cells, expanding blood vessels and reducing arterial pressure and peripheral vascular resistance. In clinics, it is used to treat angina pectoris and essential hypertension.

Telmisartan is a member of the angiotensin receptor blocker class (ARBs). In order to facilitate easier blood flow, it acts by relaxing blood vessels. This drug is used to lower blood pressure (hypertension). Bringing down high blood pressure reduces the risk of heart attacks, kidney issues, and strokes. Back discomfort, diarrhoea, and upper respiratory tract infections are typical adverse effects. Angioedema, low blood pressure, and kidney issues are examples

of serious side effects. Use whilst breastfeeding is not advised, and use during pregnancy could harm the unborn child. It functions by obstructing the actions of angiotensin II since it is an angiotensin II receptor antagonist. [2] U.V spectrophotometry and HPLC Methods are the analytical techniques reported for the determination of AZEL and TELMI alone as well as in combination with other medications.

Figure 1: Chemical structure of
Azelnidipine

Figure 2: Chemical structure of
Telmisartan

MATERIALS AND METHOD

INSTRUMENT AND REAGENTS

On a Shimadzu UV-spectrophotometer, model 1800, a spectrum was scanned (Japan). Spectral measurements were all made with the use of the UV-probe 2.34 software. A reputable firm provides the reference standard for the drugs azelnidipine and telmisartan along with certificate analysis.

PREPARATION OF STANDARD SOLUTION

AZELNIDIPINE:

Take 10mg of azelnidipine and add to a 100ml of volumetric flask. Later methanol was added to it and was sonicated for 2 to 3 minutes. A solution containing 100 g/ml of Azelnidipine was produced by shaking the flask and methanol was added to make up the volume. Take 10 ml of the solution and add it to a 100 ml volumetric flask with methanol to the proper level to create a solution containing 10 g/ml of azelnidipine. Azelnidipine solution was transferred in the appropriate volume to a separate volumetric flask with a 10ml capacity. Methanol was added to the volume as needed to achieve the desired concentrations of 1, 2, 3, 4,5, and 6.

TELMISARTAN:

Take 10mg of Telmisartan and add it to a 100ml of volumetric flask. Later methanol was added to it and was sonicated for 2 to 3 minutes. A solution containing 100 g/ml of Telmisartan was produced by shaking the flask and methanol was added to make up the volume. Take 10 ml of the solution and add it to a 100 ml volumetric flask with methanol to the proper level to create a solution containing 10 g/ml of telmisartan. Telmisartan solution aliquot was transferred in the appropriate volume to a separate volumetric flask with a 10ml capacity. Methanol was added to the volume as needed to achieve the desired concentrations of 5, 10, 15, 20, 25, and 30 µg/ml. At 271 nm (ZCP of Azelnidipine) and 234 nm (ZCP of Telmisartan), respectively, absorbance was measured for both drugs.

LINEARITY AND RANGE

Analyzing independent levels of concentrations in the range of 1-6 g/ml and 5-30 g/ml for AZEL and TELMI, respectively, allowed for the determination of the linearity response. The proposed method was used to measure the absorbance of AZEL solution at 271 nm (ZCP of Telmisartan) and 234 nm for TELMI, respectively. Plot the calibration curve of absorbance vs. concentration and determine correlation coefficient and regression line equations for AZEL and TELMI.

ACCURACY

A recovery study from formulation at three levels of standard addition—50%, 100%, and 150% of label claim—confirmed the method's accuracy in triplicate. % Recovery within 98-102% with a low standard deviation supported the method's accuracy.

REPEATABILITY (n=6)

To prepare 4 µg/ml of AZEL, 0.4 ml of the working standard solution of AZEL was put into separate 10 ml volumetric flasks, and diluted up to the mark with distilled water. Similarly, to prepare 20 µg/ml of TELMI, 2 ml of working solution was transferred to a 10ml volumetric flask. Six preparations of each concentration were made. At specific wavelengths, the absorbance of each solution was measured, and the percent RSD was computed.

INTRADAY PRECISION (n=3)

On the same day, three analyses of solutions containing 4, 5, and 6 g/ml AZEL and 20, 25, and 30 g/ml TELMI were performed in accordance with the protocol. At AZEL and TELMI wavelengths of 271 nm and 234 nm, respectively, the absorbance of solutions was measured. SD and %RSD were computed.

INTERDAY PRECISION (n=3)

On three different days, in accordance with the method, solutions containing 4, 5, and 6 g/ml AZEL and 20, 25, and 30 g/ml TELMI were analysed. At AZEL and TELMI wavelengths of 271 nm and 234 nm, respectively, the absorbance of solutions was measured. SD and %RSD were computed.

LIMIT OF DETECTION

After calculating the standard deviation (SD) of the intercepts from a calibration curve that was performed six times, the LOD was determined using the formula

$$\text{LOD} = (3.3 * \text{SD}) / \text{Slope}$$

SD stands for the Y-intercept standard deviation of the six calibration curves.

The six calibration curves' average slope is referred to as slope.

LIMIT OF QUANTITATION

The LOQ was determined using the method after a calibration curve was repeated six times and the standard deviation (SD) of the intercepts was measured using the formula:

$$\text{LOQ} = (\text{Slope} / \text{SD}) / 10$$

SD stands for the Y-intercept standard deviation of the six calibration curves.

Slope is equal to the average slope of the six calibration curves.

ESTIMATION FROM TABLETS

Twenty tablets with the claimed dosages of 40mg of telmisartan and 8mg of azelindipine were weighed, and the average weight of each tablet was calculated. Azelindipine and telmisartan's powdered equivalents were weighed and placed into a 100ml volumetric flask. Methanol was added to the flask, sonicated for 15 minutes, and then filtered. The required amount of methanol (80 µg/ml, 400 g/ml) was added. Take 1ml of the aforementioned solution and add 8 and 40 µg/ml of methanol to 10 ml of volumetric flask to make the desired concentration. Take 5ml of this solution and place it in a 10ml volumetric flask with the appropriate amounts of methanol (4 and 20 µg/ml, respectively). This solution was used for the analysis.

Fig. 1 shows the overlay spectra of the standard solutions of azelindipine and telmisartan (AZEL: 1-6 µg/ml, TELMI: 5-30 µg/ml)

Figure 2 provides the calibration curves for Azelindipine and Telmisartan, which were shown in the concentration ranges of 1 to 6 g/ml and 5 to 30 g/ml, respectively.

Fig. 2. First order derivative spectroscopic calibration curve for azelindipine and telmisartan (Abs vs Con)

Figure 3 shows the tablet mixture's first order derivative spectrum, which shows absorbance at 271 nm and 234 nm.

VALIDATION

Accuracy: The proposed approaches' accuracy was evaluated based on recovery studies. It is carried out using the standard addition procedure. The proposed method was used to conduct recovery studies by varying the levels of standard drug addition to the pre-analyzed tablet powder solution. The estimated drug amount was used to compute the percentage of recovery.

Table 1. Telmisartan and Azelnidipine Recovery for First Derivative

Mixture	% Spiking	Conc. Test taken (µg/mL)	Standard added (µg/mL)	Total con. (µg/mL)	Abs.	Conc. found (µg/mL)	% Recovery
AZEL	50%	2	1	3	-0.012	2.97	99.0
AZEL		2	1	3	-0.013	2.89	96.3
AZEL		2	1	3	-0.014	3.02	100.6
TELMI		10	5	15	-0.059	14.94	99.6
TELMI		10	5	15	-0.061	14.89	99.2
TELMI		10	5	15	-0.058	14.96	99.7
AZEL	100%	2	2	4	-0.018	3.98	99.5
AZEL		2	2	4	-0.017	4.01	100.2
AZEL		2	2	4	-0.018	3.99	99.7
TELMI		10	10	20	-0.071	20.01	100.5
TELMI		10	10	20	-0.072	19.82	99.1
TELMI		10	10	20	-0.072	19.90	99.5
AZEL	150%	2	3	5	-0.022	4.98	99.6

AZEL		2	3	5	-0.021	5.01	100.2
AZEL		2	3	5	-0.023	5.03	100.6
TELM		10	15	25	-0.083	24.87	99.5
TELM		10	15	25	-0.080	24.96	99.8
TELM		10	15	25	-0.082	25.10	100.4

By analysing a uniform tablet powder blend, the precision of the methods was established. Six replicates of the drug assay were performed using the proposed analysis methods. The relative standard deviation values were within acceptable bounds, demonstrating the methodologies' sample stability.

INTRADAY PRECISION (n=3):

According to the protocol, three analyses of solutions containing 4,5 and 6 g/ml AZEL and 20, 25, and 30 g/ml TELMI were performed on the same day. At AZEL and TELMI wavelengths of 271 nm and 234 nm, respectively, the absorbance of solutions was measured. SD and %RSD was calculated.

Table 2 shows the results of azelnidipine and telmisartan's intraday precision for first derivative

Drug	Target conc. (µg/ml)	Mean Abs. ± SD	% RSD
AZEL	4	-0.0071±0.00005	0.813
	5	-0.009±0.0001	1.111
	6	-0.0153±0.000153	0.998
TELM	20	-0.0723±0.000577	0.797
	25	-0.07867± 0.000577	0.733
	30	-0.0936±0.000577	0.615

INTERDAY PRECISION (n=3):

According to the protocol, analyses of solutions containing 4,5 and 6 g/ml of AZEL and 20, 25, and 30 g/ml of TELMI were performed on three separate days. At 271 nm of AZEL and TELMI, respectively, and 234 nm, the absorbance of solutions was measured. SD and %RSD was calculated. Table 3 contains the results that were calculated.

Table 3: results of the first derivative's intraday accuracy of azelnidipine and telmisartan

Standard Drug	Target Conc. (µg/mL)	Mean ± SD	%RSD
AZEL	4	-0.007±0.001	-1.428
	5	-0.00907± 0.00015	-1.686
	6	-0.01543±0.00020	-1.350
TELM	20	-0.07133±0.000577	-0.080
	25	-0.0833±0.001528	-1.834
	30	-0.0936±0.000577	-0.615

Repeatability

Table 4. Results of Repeatability data for AZEL and TELMI

Drug	Target conc. (µg/ml)	Abs.	Mean ±SD	%RSD
AZEL	4	-0.00781	-0.007755±0.0000575	0.7418
	4	-0.00776		
	4	-0.00769		
	4	-0.00768		
	4	-0.00778		
	4	-0.00781		

TELMI	20	-0.0747	-0.07522±0.000426	0.5663
	20	-0.0755		
	20	-0.0751		
	20	-0.0748		
	20	-0.0754		
	20	-0.0758		

Limit of Detection (LOD) and Limit of Quantification (LOQ)

Results of repeatability data for AZEL and TELMI are shown in Table 4.

The lowest concentration of an analyte that an analytical procedure can consistently distinguish from background levels is known as the limit of detection (LOD). The following equations were used in this investigation to derive the LOD and LOQ from the response's standard deviation and slope.

$$\text{LOD} = 3.3 \sigma/S$$

$$\text{LOQ} = 10 \sigma/S$$

Where S is the slope of the associated calibration graphs and is the standard deviation of the sample's signal to noise ratio. The lowest standard curve concentration that can be measured with acceptable accuracy, precision, and variability is known as the limit of quantification (LOQ). Table 4 provides the LOD and LOQ values.

Table 4 shows the LOD and LOQ results for the first derivative of azelnidipine and telmisartan.

Parameter	AZEL (at 271 nm)	TELMI (at 234 nm)
Linear Range (µg/ml)	1-6	5-30
Mean of Slope	-0.0021	-0.0024
Standard deviation of intercept	0.000308	0.001137
Limit of Detection (µg/ml)	0.4871	1.5545
Limit of Quantitation (µg/ml)	1.476	4.710

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